

RANI OF JHANSI REGIMENT: REVISITING SUBHASH CHANDRA BOSE, WOMEN AND INDIA’S FREEDOM STRUGGLE

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Abstract:

The paper is an insight into one of the most spectacular yet insufficiently studied subject of history-the first all-female Rani of Jhansi Regiment of Indian National Army in the Japanese controlled Singapore and Malaya. It will re-examine the sources to better understand women activity under this regiment in the leadership of Bose and the key figures and ideas which inspired them. An insight into the Rani of Jhansi Regiment, the first ever all-women regiment would also attract attention to the ongoing debate on whether women should be recruited in the army in combat roles and may act as an inspiration to the current leadership and young women. The desire to join the regiment was awakened in the young women by the speeches and rallies of Bose and Dr. Lakshmi Swaminathan used a door-to-door approach to ensure their participation. This work would delve deep into this regiment comprising brave women soldiers who fought for India’s liberation from British domination.

Key Words:

Rani Jhansi Regiment, INA, National Movement, Subhash Chandra Bose, Lakshmi Swaminathan, British

INTRODUCTION:

Our understanding of national movement is mostly limited to the movements, heroes, facts mentioned in books by famous authors but there are many unsung heroes of our national movement who deserve a place in not only books but even in the hearts and minds of all patriotic Indians. Rani Jhansi Regiment (RJR) of INA is one such glorious chapter in India’s freedom struggle but is lesser known to the world as no holistic work has been done specifically on this first all-women regiment from an Indian point of view. These *Ranis* served in the Indian National Army under Subhas Chandra Bose and this military creation of an all-women regiment was an innovation in 1943. The RJR was created as a part of the Burma campaign during World War II. The history of the RJR remains highly unexplored owing to the mainstream scholars who undermine the service rendered by them by putting it in a few lines. There has been a tendency in recent historiography on Nationalist struggle to overlook those forces which could not affect far reaching political change or remained outside the ambit of the mainstream Congress movement, but were significant in the sheer passion through which they worked towards uprooting the foreigner from the Indian soil.

Female participation in the movement took various forms. On one hand was the non-violent struggle of Gandhi and on the other were the revolutionaries who believed in the armed resistance to throw off the yoke of foreign invaders, the British. Among the latter, some adopted the approach of revolutionary terrorism but Bose was a pioneer in the sense that he inducted women in well planned military actions and that too with a separate regiment for them. This

was in stark contrast with the roles Gandhi had in mind for Indian women but it's unfortunate that whenever we study about the role of women in India's national movement, we mostly come across the Indian women who resisted passively and less is known about the women of RJR who fought shoulder to shoulder with the men of Indian National Army. The regiment was formed with the Japanese assistance with the aim of overthrowing British colonial rule. The announcement regarding its formation was made on 12th July 1943. RJR comprised volunteers from the expatriate Indian population in Southeast Asia and was led by Captain Lakshmi Sahgal. Only a few of them had ever been to India. Singapore was the initial nucleus where the first training camp was established and later Rangoon and Bangkok also became important centres.

THE MAKING OF THE REGIMENT AND SUBHAS CHANDRA BOSE:

Bose announced the formation of the regiment on 12th July 1943 but the blueprint of the plan started brewing in his head long before this. On his long submarine journey from the naval port of Kiel in northern Germany to the Japanese Imperial Navy's offshore outpost of Sabang, Subhash Chandra Bose, the Indian nationalist leader prepared the mission that would occupy the coming years of his life.

Bose in his autobiography mentions his high regard for his mother who had a strong will and ruled the domestic sphere. He elaborates on his philosophical faith which is progressive in nature and not dogmatic, both in moral and biological terms. In a letter to her mother, he remembers the sacrifices of Ahilya Bai, Meerabai and Durgavati who lived for the sake of Mother India and in another letter to Hemanta, he expresses his desire of Indian women taking educative roles in society. He is thrilled hearing Sarojini Naidu and finding some women extremists- Mrs. Mitra and Mrs. Dhar which is an indication of progress according to Bose.

The idea of women taking any active part in the Indian independence movement was dismissed as quite impractical until the advent of Netaji in East Asia. Although Rash Behari Bose also realised the need to integrate women into the movement, he visualised them as playing the role of nurses and doing relief work only but with the arrival of Netaji, all this changed dynamically when he gave a call for 'total mobilisation' of people and material and the need for women to come forward readily and fight shoulder to shoulder with their brothers, husbands, sons and fathers for their motherland. He gave example of armies of China and Russia where irrespective

of sex, everyone took up arms, indicating his progressive identity. The unfaltering belief and faith that these young women had in Netaji says a lot about his personality.

Sengupta has touched on Bose's interest in the emancipation of women. She refers to Bose fostering mother worship and women's political and military roles and his creation of Rani of Jhansi Regiment for the same. He wanted them to be equal partisans in order to achieve freedom. Bose started to work under the leadership of C.R. Das who recognised the need to integrate all factions of society including women. Bose kept reminding them that "more than their responsibility towards their homes, the women had an even greater duty towards their country" which is in sharp contrast to Gandhi's view of harmonious division of labour and confining women's movement for freedom to the circle of domesticity. Bose was instrumental in the formation of a separate cadre of women in the Bengal volunteers in 1928. Geraldine Forbes says that Subhash Chandra Bose was considered by many of the women revolutionaries as Bengal's champion of Women's rights. We get an idea of Bose' vision on women by looking at his speech at Vienna in 1935 in which he delineated the work being done on women in India and also in 1938, when he insisted alongwith Nehru for a separate Planning Committee for women. He openly encouraged them to look beyond the socially acceptable roles of mother or wife which is assured by analysing his bond with important women in her life- his mother, Basanti Devi; Bivabati, her young niece whom he told that the purpose of lives of women are no less valuable than the lives of man. He was immensely influenced by Vivekananda who proclaimed that "Indian women should acquire the spirit of valour and heroism and learn self-defence".

Bose' and Gandhi's views on women's roles were very different from each other. Gandhi viewed Sita as the role model emphasising woman's silent and dignified suffering as the badge of the female sex whereas Bose' radicalism supported an equal and empowered participation. Sengupta has presented a powerful testimony to Bose's idea of equality between the sexes through an analysis of Rani of Jhansi Regiment and the opinions and experiences of women in the regiment like Janaki Thevar, Manvati Arya, Anjali Ponnusamy, Rasammah Bhupalan and others. The regiment nurtured a new image of Indian women. S.R.Nathan expresses his hope for further research in his writings and speeches to understand them better and consider them worth trying in today's context.

Sisir K. Bose and Sugata Bose in their work on writings and speeches of S.C. Bose (1943-45) remark that Bose aroused the martial spirit of Indian women in East Asia when he asked them to follow the footsteps of Rani Lakshmbai of Jhansi and take up arms against the British. During his speech on the opening of the first camp for training for Rani of Jhansi Regiment at Singapore, Bose asked Indian women to march shoulder to shoulder with their brothers of Azad Hind fauj which makes it evident that he didn't want them to confine themselves to domestic works rather inspired them to lay down their lives on the battlefield for sake of India's freedom in contrast to Mahatma Gandhi. Netaji wanted to regenerate the nation and stir a new life among the womenfolk by invoking our glorious past which produced heroines like the Rani of Jhansi. He was confident that India can produce thousands of Ranis, flowers of Indian womanhood. His speech intensified the emphasis he puts on revolutionary side and bravery of women apart from the passive resistance when he reminisce about 1921 Calcutta incident when women faced lathi charge and went to jail, Rashtriya Mahila Sangh of ladies in Bengal (1928) and a volunteer corps of 500 women. Bose further mentions that he is confident of women capability in every work and thus motivates them to come forward in India's fight for freedom and fight along with their brothers against the British.

THE DEVELOPMENTS:

Bose realized that his best chance to end the British Raj lay in South East and East Asia after the defeat of Germany on 2nd February and Singapore's surrender to the Japanese on 15th February 1942. Since then, Bose sought out ways to leave Berlin for Asia. This would also bring him closer to India if based in Singapore or Rangoon in contrast to Germany where he raised a 4,000 strong Indian Legion recruited from Indian soldiers captured in North Africa.

In South East Asia, Bose's ambitious blueprint for India's liberation was based on 'total-mobilization' of Indian communities which also included an all-female Rani Jhansi Regiment. Dr. Lakshmi's tour remained instrumental in convincing many ranis and their parents to join and strengthening its growth. Bose's organization in 1928 of 300 strong women volunteers in Bengal to parade on the occasion of INC gathering was a prototype to RJR which is also evident in the section leader being referred to as 'Colonel Latika'. This time, he chose a suitable name for the regiment dedicated to Rani Lakshmbai who fought against the British during the 1857-58 Indian Mutiny. After three days of his arrival in Singapore, Bose addressed the soldiers of INA in which civilians also attended and from where Dr. Lakshmi Swaminathan, doctor and

member of the women's section of the Indian Independence League would become his most trusted ally to realize his dream of RJR and expand its operations. She has been a part of the reception committee that awaited Bose's arrival in Singapore on 3rd July. His speeches filled her with enthusiasm. Firstly she had to mobilize women for the IIL's rally to be held on 12th of July with the highlight being a women's guard of honour that would present arms to Netaji. She managed to collect the initial 20 women who were willing to be trained to present arms and went through a rigorous drilling. The nucleus of the RJR was thus formed using these 20 women. Bose told Lakshmi that the benefit of women playing such a role was twofold- the liberation of India and the end of oppression and subjugation of women by men by giving them strength of opposing exploitation and demanding equal rights. Dr. Lakshmi ensured her full support, thus beginning the multiplication of the Ranis for which she followed the door to door approach. With no training ground of their own, they began the training in a maidan within the IIL's ground for a few hours everyday. Throughout the remaining July and August, the time was taken up in military training and organizing them at headquarters, the result being the initial number 20 now rising to hundred and more. Despite various hurdles and opposition from families and relatives, the RJR kept receiving more applications.

On 30th March 1944, Dr. Lakshmi's proudest day, the regiment's first passing out parade, celebrated the first batch of officers in Singapore. The first ranis from the Singapore camp, including Janaki and Papathi Davar from Kuala Lumpur and Rasammah and Ponnammah Navarednam from Ipoh were on their way to Burma via the infamous Death Railway.

SURVIVING RANIS:

Chhabra (2015) has given a detailed account of the surviving freedom fighters. While being specifically concerned with women in RJR of INA, she describes her meeting with Veerbalaben Nagarwadia, member of the famous Dandi march who credits Gandhi for infusing the spirit of freedom struggle in the women; Nirmalaben Desai who was deeply influenced by Gandhi and briefs about Jyotisangh, started by Mridulaben on Gandhi's insistence to do something for making women self-reliant and independent; Ela Bhatt, founding member of SEWA (Self-employed women's association); Sarla Shah (influenced by Gandhi too). The extraordinary accounts of these women freedom fighters makes the impact of Gandhi on women for joining the national movement much evident. Chhabra then begins to furnish details about Bose and formation of RJR-the first ever all-women military wing of the world by him.

Captain Lakshmi Sahgal quotes Netaji-“we have so far dealt with only half of our population. Women form another half and I want them to be given a chance to start a women’s regiment, the Rani of Jhansi Regiment”. He also shared his difference with Gandhi on the need for changing methods according to the situation. Asked about her choice of leadership between Gandhi and Bose, Sahgal felt that Netaji’s ideas were definitely correct one.

The women in RJR undertook the same training as men and used to undergo minor bombings frequently. When Netaji disbanded the regiment, a large number of women wrote a petition to stay and fight for liberation. Chhabra mentions that these ranis never got recognition but we couldn’t have achieved freedom without them.

Gyan Kaur, from Burma remembers how Bose asked her to join RJR and praises the high-spirited girls and always put the needs and safety of ranis above himself. Manvati Pande Arya, another Rani describes Bose’s personality as that of a father talking to his daughters. Narrating an incident where Netaji gave his watch to a Rani to recover from a trauma, she calls him kind-hearted and thoughtful. Gauri Bhattacharya Sen gives a detailed description of her experience in the camp and regards Bose as humane, very strong and inspiring.

Three sisters-Karuna, Maya and Aruna Ganguly; Pratima Sen, Parul Bhattacharya who now runs Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose school and left his husband to join RJR as she found a purpose in life which according to her was given to them by Netaji, Momoto Mehta, Narayani Tripathi, Rajkumar Gupta, Krishna Thapar who joined RJR remenices once writing a letter to Gandhi asking to work with him but instead got a reply to stay back and spread awareness among women, children and poor; Savitri Ramkishan, Subhadra Joshi, Dhanalakshmi, P.Meenakshi, Sushila Nayar who tells Chhabra about Gandhi and his weak state after Ba’s death depicting his deep relationship with her. Chhabra views the absence of sexual abuse among the ranis as the excellent depiction of protection by Netaji and rest of INA. Her tale of journey through India, Malaysia, Singapore, Thailand and Burma in search of freedom fighters and their records about INA and Netaji is a great insight into this study.

CONCLUSION:

Our understanding of social structures in history depends to a great extent upon the position and roles of women in the society. India, although having a glorious tradition, its women's position has been precarious owing to the largely patriarchal setup. History writing treats the topic "Role of women in National Movement" monolithically and does not consider it from the

lens of various ideologues holistically. The paper tried to fill this gap by giving an account of one of the less explored but extremely important part of women history and the history of our National Movement- the Rani of Jhansi Regiment.

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